

Inclusion and Disparity: Analysis of Enrolment Patterns of Children with Special Needs and Marginalised Communities of Jammu and Kashmir

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Abstract- This study examines the status of social inclusion in elementary education in the Union Territory of Jammu and Kashmir. It specifically focuses on children with special needs and girls from different caste backgrounds. By analysing enrolment data from various districts, the study demonstrates substantial discrepancies in the incorporation of marginalized groups in the education system. The analysis reveals a greater prevalence of children with special needs in the Kashmir division as opposed to the Jammu division, with significant variations in enrolment rates depending on the nature of the condition. Moreover, the report emphasises the ongoing educational discrimination against girls belonging to marginalised caste groups. The results underscore the pressing necessity for efficacious educational policies that foster inclusivity and equity. Strengthening Village Education Committees (VECs), improving school facilities, offering comprehensive teacher training programmes, and offering financial incentives to meet marginalised communities' educational needs are just a few of the recommendations. The study also emphasises the need for increased community involvement in order to cultivate an inclusive educational atmosphere.

Keywords: social inclusion, elementary education, children with special needs, caste disparities.

1. INTRODUCTION

Inclusion is a multifaceted and disputed notion: scholars, policymakers, and professionals engage in discussions over the nature of inclusive education, its importance, and the methods for its execution. Various global organisations advocate for inclusive education as a fundamental entitlement for all students. Goal 4 of the UN 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (United Nations 2015), as well as UNESCO recommendations (2017), emphasise the importance of inclusion and equity as fundamental concepts that should shape educational policies and practices, in line with the human rights perspective.

Social inclusion has been defined by World Bank as “the process of improving the terms for individual and groups to take part in society” or more precisely “the process of improving the ability, opportunity and dignity of people, disadvantaged on the basis of their identity, to take part in society.”

Education is considered as the most important tool for the development of nation which is possible only when all the sections of the society are growing equally (Shortal,2008). India is a federal nation which has justice, liberty, equality and fraternity as its core objectives and to achieve these objectives India must incorporate social inclusion in its policies. In order to make an integrated society all the marginalised communities of the country should be included and efforts should be made to avoid exclusionary practices. Saravanakumar and Palanisamy (2013). India being a developing nation should put forth more programmes that bring social inclusion in education system. Furthermore, communities like schedule caste, schedule tribes, other backward classes, religious minorities and girls are the groups which are usually excluded from the society Agarwal (2010). Along with these, another section which can be focused are children with special needs and disability which are usually excluded and not at all being visualised for their growth. Nidhiwivedy (2013), Tansel (2002). It is observed that till now India focuses on rehabilitation of children with disability rather than on imparting education. Anjali (2013) The government should make efforts to bring inclusion in education and this can be done by educating the marginalised children and children with special needs under same roof with same cordial environment. The principle of inclusive education was adopted at “the world conference on special needs education: Access and Quality” (Salamanca, Spain 1994) and was restated at the world education forum (Dakar, Senegal 2000)

From the review of literature, it is found that many studies are conducted on social inclusion but some studies are only based on inclusion of children with disability while other are on children which are excluded on the basis of caste, patriarchy, racial, religious and class differences. The present study tries to analyse and estimate the status of social inclusion in elementary education and for that purpose we have taken into consideration both the excluded sections of the society in the first section deals in children with special needs and for that purpose we have taken into

consideration the type of disability they are possessing and their enrolment. The other section that we have considered is exclusion on the basis of caste in which we have analysed the girls enrolment on the basis of their caste, ratio of girls enrolled to the total enrolment.

2. CHILDREN WITH SPECIAL NEEDS

Children with special needs are those children which possess some kind of disability which make learning and doing other activities tough in comparison to abled children. Disability can be in the form of mental, hearing, vision, speech, cerebral palsy, autism and multiple disabilities. Special schools are made for these children but as per the changed scenario inclusion of these children in normal schools is needed. In order to call a society inclusive then all the children with special needs are learning in same schools with the non-disabled children with all the necessary conditions and support so that they feel the environment normal and learn and grow equally. On 19 January, 2005 the government of the country made a collaboration of National council of Teachers Education (NCTE) and Rehabilitation Council of India (RCI) to bring inclusion in education system. The following tables highlight the enrolment of children with special needs in UT of J&K, district wise enrolment is seen in grades I to VIII.

Table 2.1 Enrolment of Children with Special Needs in Jammu

NATURE OF DISABILITY	CWSN ENROLMENT IN JAMMU								TOTAL
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	
Blind	6	4	13	4	3	6	2	5	43
Low-vision	17	18	24	16	19	18	25	18	155
Hearing	6	6	9	9	14	7	18	15	84
Speech	15	19	19	12	12	7	15	5	104
Loco-motor	13	6	11	12	10	17	12	11	92
Mentally retarded	11	9	11	5	13	5	7	3	64
Learning	9	16	18	16	17	22	16	4	118
Cerebral palsy	0	1	0	0	1	2	2	0	6
Autism	5	4	5	10	4	10	4	10	52
Multiple	7	7	11	6	12	11	3	3	60
TOTAL	89	90	121	90	105	105	104	74	778

Source: National Institute of Educational Planning and Administration (NIEPA) and Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) 2016-17

Table 2.1 highlight the enrolment of children with special needs in Jammu district of Jammu division. Moreover, bifurcation according to the nature of disability is done and then grade wise enrolment is analysed. It is observed that the total enrolment is 778 of which enrolment in grade I is 89, grade II is 90, grade III is 121, grade IV is 90, grade V is 105, grade VI is 105, grade VII is 104, grade VIII is 74. Therefore, it is clear that grade III has highest enrolment that is 121 while lowest is in grade VIII that is 74. According to nature of disability enrolment of blind students is 43, low-vision children is 155, hearing is 84, speech is 104, loco-motor is 92, mentally retarded is 64, learning is 118, cerebral palsy is 6, autism is 52, multiple is 60. Highest enrolment is observed in children with low -vision disability which is 155, while lowest in children with cerebral palsy that is 6.

Table 2.2 Enrolment of Children with Special Needs in Doda

NATURE OF DISABILITY	CWSN ENROLMENT IN DODA								TOTAL
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	
Blind	0	3	1	3	3	3	1	2	16
Low-vision	114	151	137	73	59	49	32	14	629
Hearing	36	64	65	43	20	7	1	1	237
Speech	30	38	49	43	33	7	10	4	214
Loco-motor	42	72	34	33	21	17	4	5	228
Mentally retarded	17	27	28	16	15	7	4	2	116
Learning	1	1	2	3	2	1	0	1	11
Cerebral palsy	2	3	2	6	1	2	0	1	17
Autism	6	8	3	8	5	3	4	4	41
Multiple	5	5	10	10	3	0	1	3	37
TOTAL	253	372	331	238	162	96	57	37	1546

Source: National Institute of Educational Planning and Administration (NIEPA) and Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) 2016-17

Table 2.2 highlight the enrolment of children with special needs in Doda district of Jammu division. Moreover, bifurcation according to the nature of disability is done and then grade wise enrolment is analysed. It is observed that the total enrolment is 1546 of which enrolment in grade I is 253, grade II is 372, grade III is 331, grade IV is 238, grade V is 162, grade VI is 96, grade VII is 57, grade VIII is 37. Therefore, it is clear that grade II has highest enrolment that is 371 while lowest is in grade VIII that is 37. According to nature of disability enrolment of blind students is 16, low-vision children is 629, hearing is 237, speech is 214, loco-motor is 228, mentally retarded is 116, learning is 11, cerebral palsy is 17, autism is 41, multiple is 37. Highest enrolment is observed in children with low -vision disability which is 629, while lowest in children having learning disability that is 11.

Table 2.3 Enrolment of Children with Special Needs in Kathua

NATURE OF DISABILITY	CWSN ENROLMENT IN KATHUA								TOTAL
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	
Blind	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Low-vision	19	24	16	16	24	12	12	19	142
Hearing	2	5	2	1	4	4	4	4	26
Speech	10	16	7	9	21	4	4	5	76
Loco-motor	6	7	9	12	8	7	7	7	63
Mentally retarded	5	6	7	7	5	3	3	0	36
Learning	4	2	7	5	4	3	3	2	30
Cerebral palsy	1	1	3	0	2	0	0	0	7
Autism	6	6	7	3	7	4	4	7	44
Multiple	7	5	6	11	10	3	3	2	47
TOTAL	60	72	64	64	85	40	40	46	471

Source: National Institute of Educational Planning and Administration (NIEPA) and Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) 2016-17

Table 2.3 highlight the enrolment of children with special needs in Kathua district of Jammu division. Moreover, bifurcation according to the nature of disability is done and then grade wise enrolment is analysed. It is observed that the total enrolment is 471 of which enrolment in grade I is 60, grade II is 72, grade III is 64, grade IV is 64, grade V is 85, grade VI is 40, grade VII is 40, grade VIII is 46. Therefore, it is clear that grade V has highest enrolment that is 85 while lowest is in grade VI & VII that is 40. According to nature of disability enrolment of blind students is 0, low-vision children is 142, hearing is 26, speech is 76, loco-motor is 63, mentally retarded is 36, learning is 30, cerebral palsy is 7, autism is 44, multiple is 47. Highest enrolment is observed in children with low -vision disability which is 142, while 0 enrolment is seen in blind students.

Table 2.4 Enrolment of Children with Special Needs in Kishtwar

NATURE OF DISABILITY JAMMU	CWSN ENROLMENT IN KISHTWAR								TOTAL
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	
Blind	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Low-vision	16	20	17	24	25	16	6	13	137
Hearing	5	5	6	4	13	8	10	9	60
Speech	8	17	17	7	13	11	3	5	81
Loco-motor	12	13	13	16	14	12	11	10	101
Mentally retarded	3	3	3	3	0	0	5	1	18
Learning	2	0	2	2	2	3	1	1	13
Cerebral palsy	0	2	2	2	2	1	0	1	10
Autism	2	2	1	1	1	2	8	2	19
Multiple	6	3	11	10	10	4	2	8	54

TOTAL	54	65	72	69	80	57	46	50	493
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Source: National Institute of Educational Planning and Administration (NIEPA) and Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) 2016-17

Table 2.4 highlight the enrolment of children with special needs in Kishtwar district of Jammu division. Moreover, bifurcation according to the nature of disability is done and then grade wise enrolment is analysed. It is observed that the total enrolment is 493 of which enrolment in grade I is 54, grade II is 65, grade III is 72, grade IV is 69, grade V is 80, grade VI is 57, grade VII is 46, grade VIII is 50. Therefore, it is clear that grade V has highest enrolment that is 80 while lowest is in grade VII that is 46. According to nature of disability enrolment of blind students is 0, low-vision children is 137, hearing is 60, speech is 81, loco-motor is 101, mentally retarded is 18, learning is 13, cerebral palsy is 10, autism is 9, multiple is 54. Highest enrolment is observed in children with low -vision disability which is 137, while 0 enrolment is seen in blind students.

Table 2.5 Enrolment of Children with Special Needs in Poonch

NATURE OF DISABILITY	CWSN ENROLMENT IN POONCH								TOTAL
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	
Blind	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Low-vision	12	11	9	9	14	7	11	17	90
Hearing	5	1	1	6	3	1	1	1	19
Speech	4	6	1	6	2	1	0	2	22
Loco-motor	3	1	5	10	1	1	1	4	26
Mentally retarded	0	2	1	0	1	3	0	1	8
Learning	2	2	1	0	4	0	2	0	11
Cerebral palsy	1	2	1	1	2	3	1	0	11
Autism	5	7	2	6	6	8	6	6	46
Multiple	6	2	4	6	0	4	1	0	23
TOTAL	38	34	25	44	33	28	23	31	256

Source: National Institute of Educational Planning and Administration (NIEPA) and Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) 2016-17

Table 2.5 highlight the enrolment of children with special needs in Poonch district of Jammu division. Moreover, bifurcation according to the nature of disability is done and then grade wise enrolment is analysed. It is observed that the total enrolment is 256 of which enrolment in grade I is 38, grade II is 34, grade III is 25, grade IV is 44, grade V is 33, grade VI is 28, grade VII is 23, grade VIII is 31. Therefore, it is clear that grade IV has highest enrolment that is 44 while lowest is in grade VII that is 23. According to nature of disability enrolment of blind students is 0, low-vision children is 90, hearing is 19, speech is 22, loco-motor is 26, mentally retarded is 8, learning is 11, cerebral palsy is 11, autism is 46, multiple is 23. Highest enrolment is observed in children with low -vision disability which is 90, while 0 enrolment is seen in blind students.

Table 2.6 Enrolment of Children with Special Needs in Rajouri

NATURE OF DISABILITY	CWSN ENROLMENT IN RAJOURI								TOTAL
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	
Blind	9	5	9	9	6	1	2	1	42
Low-vision	24	22	34	24	31	28	49	29	241
Hearing	16	29	24	22	13	19	20	9	152
Speech	41	32	25	26	23	28	22	12	209
Loco-motor	45	27	44	44	39	19	33	22	273
Mentally retarded	26	8	17	25	24	6	13	4	123
Learning	12	15	20	24	20	21	14	10	136
Cerebral palsy	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	2	7
Autism	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	0	4
Multiple	15	14	17	11	17	9	2	2	87
TOTAL	188	156	191	185	175	132	156	91	1274

Source: National Institute of Educational Planning and Administration (NIEPA) and Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) 2016-17

Table 2.6 highlight the enrolment of children with special needs in Rajouri district of Jammu division. Moreover, bifurcation according to the nature of disability is done and then grade wise enrolment is analysed. It is observed that the total enrolment is 1274 of which enrolment in grade I is 188, grade II is 156, grade III is 191, grade IV is 185, grade V is 185, grade VI is 132, grade VII is 156, grade VIII is 91. Therefore, it is clear that grade III has highest enrolment that is 191 while lowest is in grade VII that is 91. According to nature of disability enrolment of blind students is 42, low-vision children is 241, hearing is 152, speech is 209, loco-motor is 273, mentally retarded is 123, learning is 136, cerebral palsy is 7, autism is 4, multiple is 87. Highest enrolment is observed in children with low-vision disability which is 241, while lowest in children with autism disability

Table 2.7 Enrolment of Children with Special Needs in Ramban

NATURE OF DISABILITY	CWSN ENROLMENT IN RAMBAN								TOTAL
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	
Blind	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Low-vision	10	16	12	11	13	7	13	10	92
Hearing	0	2	2	2	0	0	1	0	7
Speech	10	10	6	3	8	12	7	2	58
Loco-motor	4	6	10	6	17	7	10	12	72
Mentally retarded	2	5	9	1	6	5	3	0	31
Learning	3	6	11	6	5	3	4	2	40
Cerebral palsy	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	5
Autism	3	1	4	3	2	0	2	3	18
Multiple	4	3	4	3	1	4	3	1	23
TOTAL	37	49	59	36	53	38	44	30	346

Source: National Institute of Educational Planning and Administration (NIEPA) and Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) 2016-17

Table 2.7 highlight the enrolment of children with special needs in Ramban district of Jammu division. Moreover, bifurcation according to the nature of disability is done and then grade wise enrolment is analysed. It is observed that the total enrolment is 346 of which enrolment in grade I is 37, grade II is 49, grade III is 59, grade IV is 36, grade V is 53, grade VI is 38, grade VII is 44, grade VIII is 30. Therefore, it is clear that grade III has highest enrolment that is 59 while lowest is in grade VIII that is 30. According to nature of disability enrolment of blind students is 0, low-vision children is 92, hearing is 7, speech is 58, loco-motor is 72, mentally retarded is 31, learning is 40, cerebral palsy is 5, autism is 18, multiple is 23. Highest enrolment is observed in children with low-vision disability which is 92, while 0 enrolment is seen in blind students.

Table 2.8 Enrolment of Children with Special Needs in Reasi

NATURE OF DISABILITY	REASI								TOTAL
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	
Blind	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Low-vision	8	10	9	9	4	2	11	9	62
Hearing	1	3	1	1	4	1	1	2	14
Speech	1	5	2	2	1	0	1	3	15
Loco-motor	2	4	10	3	2	2	5	3	31
Mentally retarded	1	2	1	4	3	1	0	0	12
Learning	1	2	0	1	4	0	1	1	10
Cerebral palsy	1	0	0	2	0	1	0	0	4
Autism	2	1	4	0	1	0	4	1	13
Multiple	3	2	5	2	3	2	2	1	20
TOTAL	21	29	32	24	22	9	25	20	182

Source: National Institute of Educational Planning and Administration (NIEPA) and Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) 2016-17

Table 2.8 highlight the enrolment of children with special needs in Reasi district of Jammu division. Moreover, bifurcation according to the nature of disability is done and then grade wise enrolment is analysed. It is observed that the total enrolment is 182 of which enrolment in grade I is 21, grade II is 29, grade III is 32, grade IV is 24 , grade V is 22, grade VI is 9, grade VII is 25, grade VIII is 20. Therefore, it is clear that grade II has highest enrolment that is 29 while lowest is in grade VI that is 9. According to nature of disability enrolment of blind students is 1, low-vision children is 62, hearing is 14, speech is 15 , loco-motor is 31, mentally retarded is 12, learning is 10, cerebral palsy is 4, autism is 13, multiple is 20. Highest enrolment is observed in children with low -vision disability which is 62, while 1 enrolment is seen in blind students.

Table 2.9 Enrolment of Children with Special Needs in Samba

NATURE OF DISABILITY	CWSN ENROLMENT IN SAMBA								TOTAL
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	
Blind	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	0	3
Low-vision	0	1	0	0	0	2	1	1	5
Hearing	0	2	0	2	0	1	1	1	7
Speech	1	3	0	3	5	1	0	1	14
Loco-motor	2	0	1	1	4	3	1	3	15
Mentally retarded	0	3	2	0	0	1	1	1	8
Learning	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Cerebral palsy	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Autism	1	0	0	2	4	2	2	0	11
Multiple	1	2	2	5	3	1	0	2	16
TOTAL	5	12	5	13	16	12	8	9	80

Source: National Institute of Educational Planning and Administration (NIEPA) and Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) 2016-17

Table 2.9 highlight the enrolment of children with special needs in Samba district of Jammu division. Moreover, bifurcation according to the nature of disability is done and then grade wise enrolment is analysed. It is observed that the total enrolment is 80 of which enrolment in grade I is 5, grade II is 12, grade III is 5, grade IV is 13, grade V is 16, grade VI is 12, grade VII is 8, grade VIII is 9. Therefore, it is clear that grade V has highest enrolment that is 16 while lowest is in grade I and III that is 5. According to nature of disability enrolment of blind students is 3, low-vision children is 5, hearing is 7, speech is 14, loco-motor is 15, mentally retarded is 8, learning is 1, cerebral palsy is 0, autism is 11, multiple is 16. Highest enrolment is observed in children with multiple disability which is 16, while no enrolment is seen in cerebral palsy students.

Table 2.10 Enrolment of Children with Special Needs in Udhampur

NATURE OF DISABILITY	CWSN ENROLMENT IN UDHAMPUR								TOTAL
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	
Blind	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Low-vision	22	35	29	56	23	9	16	17	207
Hearing	4	5	4	4	8	3	3	7	38
Speech	11	11	9	11	17	13	3	5	80
Loco-motor	8	12	17	12	18	8	19	20	114
Mentally retarded	5	10	6	9	13	5	3	2	53
Learning	3	5	4	9	13	4	5	5	48
Cerebral palsy	0	0	0	0	1	2	0	0	3
Autism	3	5	7	3	5	4	6	1	34
Multiple	8	18	15	7	10	3	5	7	73
TOTAL	64	101	91	111	108	51	60	64	650

Source: National Institute of Educational Planning and Administration (NIEPA) and Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) 2016-17

Table 2.10 highlight the enrolment of children with special needs in Udhampur district of Jammu division. Moreover, bifurcation according to the nature of disability is done and then grade wise enrolment is analysed. It is observed that the total enrolment is 650 of which enrolment in grade I is 64, grade II is 101, grade III is 91, grade IV is 111, grade V is 108, grade VI is 51, grade VII is 60, grade VIII is 64. Therefore, it is clear that grade V has highest

enrolment that is 108 while lowest is in grade VI that is 51. According to nature of disability enrolment of blind students is 0, low-vision children is 207, hearing is 38, speech is 80, loco-motor is 114, mentally retarded is 53, learning is 48, cerebral palsy is 3, autism is 34, multiple is 73. Highest enrolment is observed in children with low -vision disability which is 207, while no enrolment is seen in blind students.

Table 2.11 Enrolment of Children with Special Needs in Anantnag

NATURE OF DISABILITY	CWSN ENROLMENT IN ANANTNAG								TOTAL
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	
Blind	0	0	0	2	3	2	2	1	10
Low-vision	36	48	78	80	75	62	59	81	519
Hearing	5	11	6	21	25	9	13	10	100
Speech	9	27	21	36	24	20	18	16	171
Loco-motor	22	39	46	36	59	40	37	43	322
Mentally retarded	13	22	35	30	28	19	25	19	191
Learning	9	27	27	25	28	19	20	23	178
Cerebral palsy	3	5	2	2	4	2	2	2	22
Autism	3	4	8	5	7	4	6	10	47
Multiple	18	27	22	25	27	19	21	14	173
TOTAL	118	210	245	262	280	196	203	219	1733

Source: National Institute of Educational Planning and Administration (NIEPA) and Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) 2016-17

Table 2.11 highlight the enrolment of children with special needs in Anantnag district of Kashmir division. Moreover, bifurcation according to the nature of disability is done and then grade wise enrolment is analysed. It is observed that the total enrolment is 1733 of which enrolment in grade I is 118, grade II is 210, grade III is 245, grade IV is 262, grade V is 280, grade VI is 196, grade VII is 203, grade VIII is 219. Therefore, it is clear that grade V has highest enrolment while lowest is in grade I that is 118. According to nature of disability enrolment of blind students is 10, low-vision children is 519, hearing is 100, speech is 171, loco-motor is 322, mentally retarded is 191, learning is 178, cerebral palsy is 22, autism is 47, multiple is 173. Highest enrolment is observed in children with low -vision disability which is 519, while lowest is in those children who are blind that is 10.

Table 2.12 Enrolment of Children with Special Needs in Badgam

NATURE OF DISABILITY	CWSN ENROLMENT IN BADGAM								TOTAL
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	
Blind	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Low-vision	17	28	20	34	21	29	27	19	195
Hearing	0	8	8	5	11	1	5	6	44
Speech	5	14	9	11	17	6	8	7	77
Loco-motor	8	8	13	6	16	11	6	9	77
Mentally retarded	3	14	13	8	11	6	4	6	65
Learning	5	11	10	15	4	3	6	9	63
Cerebral palsy	3	1	0	0	3	0	2	1	10
Autism	8	3	5	4	7	2	3	5	37
Multiple	15	11	15	11	12	7	14	11	96
TOTAL	64	98	93	94	102	65	75	73	664

Source: National Institute of Educational Planning and Administration (NIEPA) and Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) 2016-17

Table 2.12 highlight the enrolment of children with special needs in Badgam district of Kashmir division. Moreover, bifurcation according to the nature of disability is done and then grade wise enrolment is analysed. It is observed that the total enrolment is 664 of which enrolment in grade I is 64, grade II is 98, grade III is 93, grade IV is 94, grade V is 102, grade VI is 65, grade VII is 75, grade VIII is 73. Therefore, it is clear that grade V has highest enrolment that is 105 while lowest is in grade I that is 64. According to nature of disability enrolment of blind students is 0, low-vision children is 195, hearing is 44, speech is 77, loco-motor is 77, mentally retarded is 65, learning is 63, cerebral palsy is 10, autism is 37, multiple is 96. Highest enrolment is observed in children with low -vision disability which is 195, while lowest is in those children who are blind that is 0.

Table 2.13 Enrolment of Children with Special Needs in Bandipora

NATURE OF DISABILITY	CWSN ENROLMENT IN BANDIPORA								TOTAL
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	
Blind	1	3	4	4	2	4	4	1	23
Low-vision	9	5	11	13	16	13	9	10	86
Hearing	8	4	3	2	4	2	7	3	33
Speech	3	3	8	3	7	7	1	7	39
Loco-motor	4	7	1	1	7	2	4	5	31
Mentally retarded	3	2	2	2	4	3	0	1	17
Learning	0	4	6	8	4	3	15	9	49
Cerebral palsy	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	2
Autism	2	3	4	5	6	5	4	3	32
Multiple	1	3	5	5	4	3	4	3	28
TOTAL	31	34	44	43	54	44	48	42	340

Source: National Institute of Educational Planning and Administration (NIEPA) and Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) 2016-17

Table 2.13 highlight the enrolment of children with special needs in Bandipora district of Kashmir division. Moreover, bifurcation according to the nature of disability is done and then grade wise enrolment is analysed. It is observed that the total enrolment is 340 of which enrolment in grade I is 31, grade II is 34, grade III is 44, grade IV is 43, grade V is 54, grade VI is 44, grade VII is 48, grade VIII is 42. Therefore, it is clear that grade V has highest enrolment that is 54 while lowest is in grade I that is 31. According to nature of disability enrolment of blind students is 23, low-vision children is 86, hearing is 33, speech is 39, loco-motor is 31, mentally retarded is 17, learning is 49, cerebral palsy is 2, autism is 32, multiple is 28. Highest enrolment is observed in children with low -vision disability which is 86, while lowest is in those children who are cerebral palsy that is 2.

Table 2.14 Enrolment of Children with Special Needs in Baramula

NATURE OF DISABILITY	CWSN ENROLMENT IN BARAMULA								TOTAL
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	
Blind	17	11	11	5	4	2	10	7	67
Low-vision	16	28	361	32	311	26	298	28	1100
Hearing	3	31	5	3	10	5	148	3	208
Speech	31	16	12	16	11	4	12	181	283
Loco-motor	11	15	20	135	11	14	14	293	513
Mentally retarded	11	22	9	18	15	14	11	9	109
Learning	5	12	7	18	6	122	10	4	184
Cerebral palsy	1	1	4	1	7	1	4	0	19
Autism	2	3	7	0	0	0	0	0	12
Multiple	16	29	34	108	18	259	9	8	481
TOTAL	113	168	470	336	393	447	516	533	2976

Source: National Institute of Educational Planning and Administration (NIEPA) and Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) 2016-17

Table 2.14 highlight the enrolment of children with special needs in Baramulla district of Kashmir division. Moreover, bifurcation according to the nature of disability is done and then grade wise enrolment is analysed. It is observed that the total enrolment is 2976 of which enrolment in grade I is 113, grade II is 168, grade III is 470, grade IV is 336, grade V is 393, grade VI is 447, grade VII is 516, grade VIII is 533. Therefore, it is clear that grade VII has highest enrolment that is 516 while lowest is in grade I that is 113. According to nature of disability enrolment of blind students is 67, low-vision children is 1100, hearing is 208, speech is 283, loco-motor is 513, mentally retarded is 109, learning is 184, cerebral palsy is 19, autism is 12, multiple is 481. Highest enrolment is observed in children with low -vision disability which is 1100, while lowest is in those children with autism that is 12.

Table 2.15 Enrolment of Children with Special Needs in Ganderbal

NATURE OF DISABILITY	CWSN ENROLMENT GANDERBAL								TOTAL
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	
Blind	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	2

Low-vision	14	8	13	18	23	10	12	17	115
Hearing	2	3	4	6	7	1	1	9	33
Speech	8	9	10	9	10	3	3	4	56
Loco-motor	5	9	8	12	13	8	2	5	62
Mentally retarded	3	8	12	5	3	5	3	6	45
Learning	9	10	4	13	17	5	7	8	73
Cerebral palsy	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	3
Autism	0	3	1	1	0	2	1	0	8
Multiple	4	6	3	5	6	6	2	4	36
TOTAL	46	57	55	70	80	40	32	53	433

Source: National Institute of Educational Planning and Administration (NIEPA) and Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) 2016-17

Table 2.15 highlight the enrolment of children with special needs in Ganderbal district of Kashmir division. Moreover, bifurcation according to the nature of disability is done and then grade wise enrolment is analysed. It is observed that the total enrolment is 433 of which enrolment in grade I is 46, grade II is 57, grade III is 55, grade IV is 70, grade V is 80, grade VI is 40, grade VII is 32, grade VIII is 53. Therefore, it is clear that grade V has highest enrolment that is 80 while lowest is in grade I that is 32. According to nature of disability enrolment of blind students is 2, low-vision children is 115, hearing is 33, speech is 56, loco-motor is 62, mentally retarded is 45, learning is 73, cerebral palsy is 3, autism is 8, multiple is 36. Highest enrolment is observed in children with low -vision disability which is 115, while lowest is in blind children that is 3.

Table 2.16 Enrolment of Children with Special Needs in Kulgam

NATURE OF DISABILITY	CWSN ENROLMENT KULGAM								TOTAL
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	
Blind	0	1	2	4	1	2	1	1	12
Low-vision	15	16	25	18	18	16	18	18	144
Hearing	4	7	7	6	7	4	3	4	42
Speech	22	12	7	11	13	16	6	8	95
Loco-motor	13	17	11	19	19	27	11	17	134
Mentally retarded	12	10	6	14	13	10	7	6	78
Learning	3	5	5	5	13	6	9	8	54
Cerebral palsy	2	0	2	0	0	2	1	0	7
Autism	3	5	4	5	5	2	7	2	33
Multiple	22	14	29	29	27	12	14	10	157
TOTAL	96	87	98	111	116	97	77	74	756

Source: National Institute of Educational Planning and Administration (NIEPA) and Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) 2016-17

Table 2.16 highlight the enrolment of children with special needs in Kulgam district of Kashmir division. Moreover, bifurcation according to the nature of disability is done and then grade wise enrolment is analysed. It is observed that the total enrolment is 756 of which enrolment in grade I is 96, grade II is 87, grade III is 98, grade IV is 111, grade V is 116, grade VI is 97, grade VII is 77, grade VIII is 74. Therefore, it is clear that grade V has highest enrolment that is 116 while lowest is in grade VIII that is 74. According to nature of disability enrolment of blind students is 12, low-vision children is 144, hearing is 42, speech is 95, loco-motor is 134, mentally retarded is 78, learning is 54, cerebral palsy is 7, autism is 33, multiple is 157. Highest enrolment is observed in children with multiple disability which is 157, while lowest is in children with cerebral palsy that is 3.

Table 2.17 Enrolment of Children with Special Needs in Kupwara

NATURE OF DISABILITY	CWSN ENROLMENT KUPWARA								TOTAL
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	
Blind	3	5	15	3	7	6	11	5	55
Low-vision	43	74	65	57	67	61	82	63	512
Hearing	17	20	34	29	39	34	35	23	231
Speech	21	27	31	31	21	16	21	13	181

Loco-motor	23	21	31	36	28	22	12	25	198
Mentally retarded	19	12	19	22	18	7	11	10	118
Learning	14	29	28	26	18	14	21	16	166
Cerebral palsy	1	5	4	8	4	6	4	5	37
Autism	2	3	3	10	11	0	3	6	38
Multiple	20	15	24	17	17	24	17	13	147
TOTAL	163	211	254	239	230	190	217	179	1683

Source: National Institute of Educational Planning and Administration (NIEPA) and Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) 2016-17

Table 2.17 highlight the enrolment of children with special needs in Kupwara district of Kashmir division. Moreover, bifurcation according to the nature of disability is done and then grade wise enrolment is analysed. It is observed that the total enrolment is 1683 of which enrolment in grade I is 163, grade II is 211, grade III is 254, grade IV is 239, grade V is 230, grade VI is 190, grade VII is 217, grade VIII is 179. Therefore, it is clear that grade III has highest enrolment that is 256 while lowest is in grade I that is 163. According to nature of disability enrolment of blind students is 55, low-vision children is 512, hearing is 231, speech is 181, loco-motor is 198, mentally retarded is 118, learning is 166, cerebral palsy is 37, autism is 38, multiple is 147. Highest enrolment is observed in children with low-vision which is 157, while lowest is in children with cerebral palsy that is 37.

Table 2.18 Enrolment of Children with Special Needs in Pulwama

NATURE OF DISABILITY	CWSN ENROLMENT PULWAMA								TOTAL
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	
Blind	0	0	1	0	0	1	4	3	9
Low-vision	27	38	42	57	48	68	82	78	440
Hearing	3	6	3	9	8	7	4	5	45
Speech	13	18	12	17	13	9	15	4	101
Loco-motor	13	14	20	16	24	12	14	18	131
Mentally retarded	13	14	23	19	25	17	18	16	145
Learning	8	5	12	12	12	12	11	7	79
Cerebral palsy	0	5	7	4	6	0	5	2	29
Autism	2	3	5	1	5	4	1	6	27
Multiple	7	19	15	9	12	12	13	10	97
TOTAL	86	122	140	144	153	142	167	149	1103

Source: National Institute of Educational Planning and Administration (NIEPA) and Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) 2016-17

Table 2.18 highlight the enrolment of children with special needs in Kupwara district of Kashmir division. Moreover, bifurcation according to the nature of disability is done and then grade wise enrolment is analysed. It is observed that the total enrolment is 1103 of which enrolment in grade I is 86, grade II is 122, grade III is 140, grade IV is 144, grade V is 153, grade VI is 142, grade VII is 167, grade VIII is 149. Therefore, it is clear that grade VII has highest enrolment that is 167 while lowest is in grade I that is 86. According to nature of disability enrolment of blind students is 9, low-vision children is 440, hearing is 45, speech is 101, loco-motor is 131, mentally retarded is 145, learning is 79, cerebral palsy is 29, autism is 27, multiple is 97. Highest enrolment is observed in children with low-vision which is 440, while lowest is in children with autism that is 37.

Table 2.19 Enrolment of Children with Special Needs in Shopian

NATURE OF DISABILITY	CWSN ENROLMENT IN SHOPIAN								TOTAL
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	
Blind	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Low-vision	3	6	3	2	4	4	10	4	36
Hearing	2	1	1	1	2	2	1	1	11
Speech	1	1	2	1	0	1	0	0	6
Loco-motor	0	1	0	2	3	1	0	0	7
Mentally retarded	0	3	0	3	1	0	2	1	10
Learning	0	5	1	3	4	3	1	0	17
Cerebral palsy	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	2

Autism	0	2	1	2	2	2	1	3	13
Multiple	2	0	2	0	2	2	0	0	8
TOTAL	8	19	11	14	19	15	15	9	110

Source: National Institute of Educational Planning and Administration (NIEPA) and Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) 2016-17

Table 2.19 highlight the enrolment of children with special needs in Kupwara district of Kashmir division. Moreover, bifurcation according to the nature of disability is done and then grade wise enrolment is analysed. It is observed that the total enrolment is 110 of which enrolment in grade I is 8, grade II is 19, grade III is 11, grade IV is 14, grade V is 19, grade VI is 15, grade VII is 15, grade VIII is 9. Therefore, it is clear that grade II and V has highest enrolment that is 19 while lowest is in grade VIII that is 9. According to nature of disability enrolment of blind students is 0, low-vision children is 36, hearing is 11, speech is 6, loco-motor is 7, mentally retarded is 10, learning is 17, cerebral palsy is 2, autism is 13, multiple is 8. Highest enrolment is observed in children with low-vision which is 36, while lowest is in children with cerebral palsy that is 2.

Table 2.20 Enrolment of Children with Special Needs in Srinagar

NATURE OF DISABILITY	CWSN ENROLMENT IN SRINAGAR								
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	TOTAL
Blind	5	3	2	4	2	3	2	2	23
Low-vision	24	82	83	88	95	81	116	110	679
Hearing	17	13	15	22	20	14	14	16	131
Speech	16	9	12	13	11	8	9	4	82
Loco-motor	8	17	14	8	8	9	8	6	78
Mentally retarded	10	10	11	5	9	2	8	4	59
Learning	21	46	59	59	67	49	46	32	379
Cerebral palsy	3	1	2	1	1	0	0	0	8
Autism	0	2	4	2	3	2	5	2	20
Multiple	10	12	9	6	9	4	0	3	53
TOTAL	114	195	211	208	225	172	208	179	1512

Source: National Institute of Educational Planning and Administration (NIEPA) and Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) 2016-17

Table 2.20 highlight the enrolment of children with special needs in Srinagar district of Kashmir division. Moreover, bifurcation according to the nature of disability is done and then grade wise enrolment is analysed. It is observed that the total enrolment is 1512 of which enrolment in grade I is 114, grade II is 195, grade III is 211, grade IV is 208, grade V is 225, grade VI is 172, grade VII is 208, grade VIII is 179. Therefore, it is clear that grade V has highest enrolment that is 225 while lowest is in grade I that is 114. According to nature of disability enrolment of blind students is 23, low-vision children is 679, hearing is 131, speech is 82, loco-motor is 78, mentally retarded is 59, learning is 379, cerebral palsy is 8, autism is 20, multiple is 53. Highest enrolment is observed in children with low-vision which is 679, while lowest is in children with cerebral palsy that is 8.

3. ENROLMENT ON THE BASIS OF CASTE

Social inclusion on the basis of caste is very important in order to make an integrated society. Schedule Caste (SC), Schedule Tribe (ST) and Other Backward Classes (OBC) are the caste that are usually considered as marginalised and are excluded from the mainstream communities. In today's world a very serious human right issue is discrimination on the basis of caste and this can be reduced by educating the children of these communities. The present section tries to analyse the total enrolment and girl's enrolment of Schedule Caste, Schedule Tribe and Other Backward Classes group in primary and upper primary level of education in UT of Jammu and Kashmir.

Table 3.1 percentage enrolment of schedule caste children in Jammu division

SCHEDULE CASTE ENROLMENT IN PERCENTAGE				
Districts	Primary		Upper primary	
	Total Enrolment	Girl's Enrolment	Total Enrolment	Girl's Enrolment

Jammu	25.4	46.4	26.4	47
Doda	13.2	49.9	13.8	49.3
Kathua	25.5	46.7	25.9	48
Kishtwar	6.9	47.8	7	46.9
Poonch	0.6	41.1	0.4	41
Rajouri	6.4	47.6	7.1	46.2
Ramban	5.9	47.9	6.3	48.9
Reasi	10.1	48	13.1	50.7
Samba	34.1	45.6	33.3	45.8
Udhampur	29	48.1	27.9	46.3

Source: National Institute of Educational Planning and Administration (NIEPA) and Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) 2016-17

Table 3.1 shows percentage enrolment of schedule caste children in jammu division and for that purpose total enrolment and girl's enrolment in primary and upper primary level of education is taken in to consideration. For primary level of education in Jammu district the total enrolment is 25.4per cent of which 46.4per cent is girl's enrolment. similarly, in Doda total enrolment is 13.2per cent out of which enrolment of girl's is 49.9per cent, in Kathua 46.7 per cent of girls are enrolled from 25.5per cent of total enrolment. In Kishtwar total enrolment is 6.9per cent while in Poonch it is 0.6per cent out of which enrolled girls are 47.8per cent in Kishtwar and 41.1per cent in Poonch. Rajouri has 6.4per cent total enrolled children which has 47.6per cent as girl's students. Likewise, Ramban has 5.9per cent total enrolled students with 47.9per cent being girl's students, Reasi has 10.1per cent total enrolment and 48per cent girl's enrolment. Samba and Udhampur has total enrolment of 34.1per cent and 29per cent respectively out of which girl's enrolment is 45.6per cent in Samba and 48.1per cent in Udhampur. Therefore, it is clear that highest total enrolment is seen in Samba district that is 34.1per cent while lowest in Poonch that is 0.6per cent. it is also observed that in all the districts enrolment of girl's is above 40per cent Doda has highest enrolment of girls while Poonch is again lowest among all with 41.1per cent. Moreover, for upper primary level of education in jammu district the total enrolment is 26.4per cent of which 47per cent is girl's enrolment. Similarly, in Doda total enrolment is 13.8per cent out of which enrolment of girl's is 49.3per cent, in Kathua 48 per cent of girls are enrolled from 25.9per cent of total enrolment. In Kishtwar total enrolment is 7per cent while in Poonch it is 0.4per cent out of which enrolled girls are 46.9per cent in Kishtwar and 41per cent in Poonch. Rajouri has 7.1per cent total enrolled children which has 46.2per cent as girl's students. Likewise, Ramban has 6.3per cent total enrolled students with 48.9per cent being girl's students, Reasi has 13.1per cent total enrolment and 50.7per cent girl's enrolment. Samba and Udhampur has total enrolment of 33.3per cent and 27.9per cent respectively out of which girl's enrolment is 45.8per cent in Samba and 46.3per cent in Udhampur. Therefore, it is clear that highest total enrolment is seen in Samba district that is 33.3per cent while lowest in Poonch that is 0.4per cent. it is also observed that in all the district's enrolment of girl's is above 40per cent, Reasi has highest enrolment of girls that is 50.7per cent while Poonch is again lowest among all with 41.1per cent.

Henceforth it is analysed that in Jammu division, Poonch has lowest total enrolment as well as girl's enrolment at both primary and upper primary level of education while highest total enrolment is observed in Samba but it does not have highest girl's enrolment in both primary and upper primary level of education. For primary level Doda has highest enrolled percentage of girls while for upper primary level of education Reasi is above all the districts.

Table 3.2 percentage enrolment of schedule tribe children in Jammu division

SCHEDULE TRIBE ENROLMENT IN PERCENTAGE				
Districts	Primary		Upper primary	
	Total Enrolment	Girl's Enrolment	Total Enrolment	Girl's Enrolment
Jammu	7.4	47.3	6.2	47.1
Doda	12.1	46.9	10.9	45.9
Kathua	13.1	46.6	9.8	44.3
Kishtwar	19.6	43.3	12.2	38.8
Poonch	44.7	47.6	40.6	48.1
Rajouri	42.2	48.1	36.6	47.5
Ramban	15.3	46.3	13	43.6
Reasi	30.3	46	25.2	46.5
Samba	8.1	46.2	6.1	41.5
Udhampur	12.9	46.9	10.7	44

Source: National Institute of Educational Planning and Administration (NIEPA) and Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) 2016-17

Table 3.2 shows percentage enrolment of schedule tribe children in jammu division and for that purpose total enrolment and girl's enrolment in primary and upper primary level of education is taken in to consideration. For primary level of education in jammu district the total enrolment is 7.4per cent of which 47.3per cent is girl's enrolment. similarly, in Doda total enrolment is 12.1per cent out of which enrolment of girl's is 46.9per cent, in Kathua 46.6per cent of girls are enrolled from 13.1per cent of total enrolment. In Kishtwar total enrolment is 19.6per cent while in Poonch it is 44.7per cent out of which enrolled girls are 43.3per cent in Kishtwar and 47.6per cent in Poonch. Rajouri has 42.2per cent total enrolled children which has 48.1per cent as girl's students. Likewise, Ramban has 15.3per cent total enrolled students with 46.3per cent being girl's students, Reasi has 30.3per cent total enrolment and 46per cent girl's enrolment. Samba and Udhampur has total enrolment of 8.1per cent and 12.9per cent respectively out of which girl's enrolment is 46.2per cent in Samba and 46.9per cent in Udhampur. Therefore, it is clear that highest total enrolment is seen in Poonch district that is 44.7per cent while lowest in Jammu that is 7.4per cent. it is also observed that in all the district's enrolment of girl's is above 40per cent Rajouri has highest enrolment of girls that is 48.1per cent while Kishtwar is lowest among all with 43.3per cent. Moreover, for upper primary level of education in jammu district the total enrolment is 6.2per cent of which 47.1per cent is girl's enrolment. Similarly, in Doda total enrolment is 10.9per cent out of which enrolment of girl's is 45.9per cent, in Kathua 44.3per cent of girls are enrolled from 9.8per cent of total enrolment. In Kishtwar total enrolment is 12.2per cent while in Poonch it is 40.6per cent out of which enrolled girls are 38.8per cent in Kishtwar and 48.1per cent in Poonch. Rajouri has 36.6per cent total enrolled children which has 47.5per cent as girl's students. Likewise, Ramban has 13per cent total enrolled students with 43.6per cent being girl's students, Reasi has 25.2per cent total enrolment and 46.5per cent girl's enrolment. Samba and Udhampur has total enrolment of 6.1per cent and 10.7per cent respectively out of which girl's enrolment is 41.5per cent in Samba and 44per cent in Udhampur. Therefore, it is clear that highest total enrolment is seen in Poonch district that is 40.6per cent while lowest in Samba that is 6.1per cent. it is also observed that in all the district's enrolment of girl's is above 35per cent, Poonch has highest enrolment of girls that is 48.1per cent while Kishtwar is lowest among all with 38.8per cent.

Henceforth it is analysed that Poonch has highest total enrolment in both primary and upper primary level of education while for primary level jammu is lowest among all and for upper primary level samba is lowest among all. Highest girls enrolment is 48.1per cent which is in Rajouri for primary education and for upper primary it is in Poonch while lowest is in Kishtwar for both primary and upper primary level of education.

Table 3.3 percentage enrolment of other backward class children in Jammu division

OTHER BACKWARD CASTE ENROLMENT IN PERCENTAGE				
Districts	Primary		Upper primary	
	Total Enrolment	Girl's Enrolment	Total Enrolment	Girl's Enrolment
Jammu	6.5	43.8	6.8	45.5
Doda	0	0	0	0
Kathua	7.8	45	8.3	42.8
Kishtwar	6.2	48.6	7.3	50.5
Poonch	8.7	47.5	8.4	48.7
Rajouri	4.1	48.3	4.6	51.6
Ramban	6.5	44.6	5.4	43.2
Reasi	14.3	46.6	13	45
Samba	10.9	43.1	11.5	45
Udhampur	4	46.8	4.3	45.8

Source: National Institute of Educational Planning and Administration (NIEPA) and Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) 2016-17

Table 3.3 shows percentage enrolment of other backward class children in jammu division and for that purpose total enrolment and girl's enrolment in primary and upper primary level of education is taken in to consideration. For primary level of education in jammu district the total enrolment is 6.5per cent of which 43.8per cent is girl's enrolment. In Doda total enrolment is 0, in Kathua 45per cent of girls are enrolled from 7.8per cent of total enrolment. In Kishtwar total enrolment is 6.2per cent while in Poonch it is 8.7per cent out of which enrolled girls are 45per cent. in Kishtwar and 48.6per cent in Poonch. Rajouri has 4.1per cent total enrolled children which has 48.3per cent as girl's students.

Likewise, Ramban has 6.5per cent total enrolled students with 44.6per cent being girl's students, Reasi has 14.3per cent total enrolment and 46.6per cent girl's enrolment. Samba and Udhampur has total enrolment of 10.9per cent and 4per cent respectively out of which girl's enrolment is 43.1per cent in Samba and 46.8per cent in Udhampur. Therefore, it is clear that highest total enrolment is seen in Reasi district that is 14.3per cent while lowest in Doda that is 0per cent. It is also observed that in all the district's enrolment of girl's is above 40per cent except Doda where it is 0 Kishtwar has highest enrolment of girls that is 48.6per cent. Moreover, for upper primary level of education in jammu district the total enrolment is 6.8per cent of which 45.5per cent is girl's enrolment. In Doda total enrolment is 0, in Kathua 42.8per cent of girls are enrolled from 8.3per cent of total enrolment. In Kishtwar total enrolment is 7.3per cent while in Poonch it is 8.4per cent out of which enrolled girls are 50.5per cent in Kishtwar and 48.7per cent in Poonch. Rajouri has 4.6per cent total enrolled children which has 51.6per cent as girl's students. Likewise, Ramban has 5.4per cent total enrolled students with 43.2per cent being girl's students, Reasi has 13per cent total enrolment and 45per cent girl's enrolment. Samba and Udhampur has total enrolment of 11.5per cent and 4.3per cent respectively out of which girl's enrolment is 45per cent in Samba and 45.8per cent in Udhampur. Therefore, it is clear that highest total enrolment is seen in Samba district that is 11.5per cent while lowest in Doda that is 0per cent. It is also observed that in all the district's enrolment of girl's is above 40 except in Doda where it is 0, Rajouri has highest enrolment of girls that is 51.6per cent.

Therefore, it is observed that doda is the only district which has 0 enrolment in both primary and upper primary level of education while Reasi has highest total as well as girl's enrolment in both levels of education.

Table 3.4 percentage enrolment of schedule tribe children in Kashmir division

SCHEDULE TRIBE ENROLMENT IN PERCENTAGE				
Districts	Primary		Upper primary	
	Total Enrolment	Girl's Enrolment	Total Enrolment	Girl's Enrolment
Anantnag	16.5	46.5	11.7	47.1
Badgam	4.8	48.7	4	46.5
Bandipora	25.8	47.8	22.7	46.5
Baramula	5.2	46.3	4.1	44.7
Ganderbal	24.7	49.8	18.5	46.9
Kulgam	9.9	47.2	6.2	49.8
Kupwara	12.2	49.3	10.3	45.4
Pulwama	9.2	46.1	5.7	46.2
Shopian	15.1	47.6	9.9	45.3
Srinagar	2.6	48.2	2	44

Source: National Institute of Educational Planning and Administration (NIEPA) and Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) 2016-17

Table 3.4 shows percentage enrolment of schedule tribe children in Kashmir division and for that purpose total enrolment and girl's enrolment in primary and upper primary level of education is taken in to consideration. For primary level of education in Anantnag district the total enrolment is 16.5per cent of which 46.5per cent is girl's enrolment. Similarly, in Badgam total enrolment is 4.8per cent out of which enrolment of girl's is 48.7per cent, in Bandipora 47.8per cent of girls are enrolled from 25.8per cent of total enrolment. In Baramula total enrolment is 5.2per cent while in Ganderbal it is 24.7per cent out of which enrolled girls are 46.3per cent in Baramula and 49.8per cent in Ganderbal. Kulgam has 9.9per cent total enrolled children which has 47.2per cent as girl's students. Likewise, Kupwara has 12.2per cent total enrolled students with 49.3per cent being girl's students, Pulwama has 9.2per cent total enrolment and 46.1per cent girl's enrolment. Shopian and Srinagar has total enrolment of 15.1per cent and 2.6per cent respectively out of which girl's enrolment is 47.6per cent in Shopian and 48.2per cent in Srinagar. Therefore, it is clear that highest total enrolment is seen in Bandipora district that is 25.8per cent while lowest in Srinagar that is 2.6per cent. it is also observed that in all the district's enrolment of girl's is above 45per cent, Ganderbal has highest enrolment of girls that is 49.8per cent while Pulwama is lowest among all with 46.1per cent. Moreover, for upper primary level of education in Anantnag district the total enrolment is 11.7per cent of which 47.1per cent is girl's enrolment. Similarly, in Badgam total enrolment is 4per cent out of which enrolment of girl's is 46.5per cent, in Bandipora 46.5per cent of girls are enrolled from 22.7per cent of total enrolment. In Baramula total enrolment is 4.1per cent while in Ganderbal it is 18.5per cent out of which enrolled girls are 44.7 in Baramula and 46.9per cent in Ganderbal. Kulgam has 6.2per cent total enrolled children which has 49.8per cent as girl's students. Likewise, Kupwara has 10.3per cent total enrolled students with 45.4per cent being girl's students, Pulwama has 5.7per cent total enrolment and 46.2per cent girl's enrolment. Shopian and Srinagar has total enrolment of 9.9per cent and 2per cent respectively out of which girl's enrolment is 45.3per cent in Shopian and 44per cent in Srinagar. Therefore, it is clear that highest total enrolment is seen in Bandipora district that is 22.7per cent while lowest in Srinagar that is 2per cent. it is also observed that in all the district's enrolment of

girl's is above 40per cent, Kulgam has highest enrolment of girls that is 49.8per cent while Srinagar is lowest among all with 44per cent.

Henceforth, we can conclude that Bandipora has highest no. of total enrolment in both primary and upper primary level of education while Srinagar is lowest among all. With 49.8per cent Ganderbal is highest among all for girl's enrolment in primary education similarly Kulgam is for upper primary level of education. Pulwama and Srinagar rank lowest among all for primary and upper primary level of education respectively.

Table 3.5 percentage enrolment of other backward class children in Kashmir division

OTHER BACKWARD CLASS ENROLMENT IN PERCENTAGE				
Districts	Primary		Upper primary	
	Total Enrolment	Girl's Enrolment	Total Enrolment	Girl's Enrolment
Anantnag	11.6	48.5	11.6	49.5
Badgam	13.6	50.4	12.1	50.8
Bandipora	16.6	50	16.3	48.4
Baramula	23.5	49.6	22.7	49.5
Ganderbal	22.7	50	21.4	50.6
Kulgam	0	0	0	0
Kupwara	16.4	48.6	16	46.9
Pulwama	15.5	48.7	15.7	51.7
Shopian	0	0	0	0
Srinagar	2.7	48.4	2.1	48.6

Source: National Institute of Educational Planning and Administration (NIEPA) and Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) 2016-17

Table 3.5 shows percentage enrolment of other backward class children in Kashmir division and for that purpose total enrolment and girl's enrolment in primary and upper primary level of education is taken in to consideration. For primary level of education in Anantnag district the total enrolment is 11.6per cent of which 48.5per cent is girl's enrolment. Similarly, in Badgam total enrolment is 13.6per cent out of which enrolment of girl's is 50.4per cent, in Bandipora 50per cent of girls are enrolled from 16.6per cent of total enrolment. In Baramula total enrolment is 23.5per cent while in Ganderbal it is 22.7per cent out of which enrolled girls are 49.6per cent in Baramula and 50per cent in Ganderbal. Kulgam and Shopian has 0per cent total enrolled children. Kupwara has 16.4per cent total enrolled students with 48.6per cent being girl's students. Likewise, Pulwama has 15.5per cent total enrolment and 48.7per cent girl's enrolment. lastly Srinagar has 2.7 as total enrolment of which 48.4per cent enrolment is of girls. Therefore, it is clear that highest total enrolment is seen in Baramulla district that is 23.5per cent while lowest in Kulgam and Shopian that is 0per cent. Further Badgam has highest enrolment of girls that is 50.4per cent. Moreover, for upper primary level of education in Anantnag district the total enrolment is 11.6per cent of which 49.5per cent is girl's enrolment. Similarly, in Badgam total enrolment is 12.1per cent out of which enrolment of girl's is 50.8per cent, in Bandipora 48.4per cent of girls are enrolled from 16.3per cent of total enrolment. In Baramula total enrolment is 22.7per cent while in Ganderbal it is 21.4per cent out of which enrolled girls are 49.5per cent in Baramula and 50.6per cent in Ganderbal. Kulgam and Shopian has 0per cent total enrolled children, Kupwara has 16per cent total enrolled students with 46.9per cent being girl's students. Likewise, Pulwama has 15.7per cent total enrolment and 51.7per cent girl's enrolment. lastly, Srinagar has total enrolment of 2.1per cent out of which girl's enrolment is 48.6per cent. Therefore, it is clear that highest total enrolment is seen in Baramula district that is 22.7per cent while lowest in Kulgam and Kupwara that is 0per cent which further makes girls enrolment in these two districts as zero. Moreover, Pulwama ranks 1st in enrolment of girls with 51.7per cent which is a good sign of social inclusion.

Therefore, we can conclude that Kulgam and Shopian are the two districts in Kashmir division that has no enrolment in both primary and upper primary level of education. Baramula has highest total enrolment in both primary and upper primary level of education while Badgam has highest girls' enrolment in both primary and upper primary level of education.

4. CONCLUSION

The analysis of social inclusion in elementary schools in Jammu and Kashmir reveals notable discrepancies in enrolment patterns throughout the region. The number of children with special needs is higher in the Kashmir division than in the Jammu division, with an additional 5234 children enrolled in Kashmir. Baramulla district has the largest enrolment of children with special needs, while Samba district has the lowest.

The study also emphasises that children from disadvantaged communities (SC, ST, and OBC) are not receiving complete advantages from educational programs Suri (2014). This highlights the importance of the Village Education Committee

(VEC) in playing a vital role in guaranteeing the delivery of high-quality education to these specific populations Manjeet and Sharma (2008).

In Jammu division, the ST communities have the highest enrolment in primary and upper primary schools. Among girls, the elementary level has the highest enrolment rate for children from the SC category, while at the upper primary level, children from the OBC category have the highest enrolment rate. In the Kashmir division, the ST communities have the largest number of students enrolled at the primary level. However, both ST and OBC tribes have the highest enrolment at the upper primary level. Among girls, communities classified as OBC exhibit the greatest enrolment rates in both primary and higher primary education levels.

According to district-level statistics, Badgam has the highest girls' enrolment, while Baramulla has the highest total enrolment in the Kashmir division for both primary and upper primary levels. Conversely, Kulgam and Shopian districts have reported zero enrolment at both primary and secondary education levels. Based on district-level data, Badgam has the highest number of girls enrolled, whereas Baramulla has the highest overall enrolment in the Kashmir division for both primary and upper primary levels. In contrast, Kulgam and Shopian districts have recorded no students enrolled at either the basic or secondary education levels.

The examination of enrolment patterns in primary schools in Jammu and Kashmir reveals various significant policy consequences. In order to rectify the significant disparities, it is imperative to establish focused educational initiatives in low-enrolment districts Nidhiwivedy (2013) such as Kulgam and Shopian, which should encompass community engagement and informative campaigns. Enhancing the Village Education Committee (VEC) through targeted training will ensure better assistance for marginalized groups and efficient resource allocation Saravanakumar and Palanisamy (2013). It is critical to strengthen special needs education by providing teacher training, allocating more resources, and improving infrastructure Basumatary (2012), especially in areas like Baramulla with a large number of students with special needs. Implementing incentives such as scholarships, complimentary uniforms, and subsidised mid-day meals can effectively alleviate economic obstacles to education for the SC, ST, and OBC groups Ramachandran (2003) Biswajit and Indrajit (2015) Thangaraj (2002). Implementing gender-specific interventions such as providing safe transportation and separate sanitation facilities will effectively promote increased enrollment among girls. Reddy (2001)

A strong monitoring and evaluation structure will enable evidence-based modifications to policy, while combining education policies with wider social welfare programmes will tackle fundamental socio-economic problems. Sankar (2007) Involving local communities in the conception and execution of these programs will ensure that marginalized groups' needs are met, promoting a more inclusive and fairer educational atmosphere in the area.

5. LIMITATIONS

The examination of social inclusion in primary schools in Jammu and Kashmir, although thorough, does have certain constraints. A major limitation is the dependability and precision of the utilized data. The study relies on data sourced from governmental and educational institutions, which may not consistently reflect the most up-to-date or completely precise information. Differences in the methods used to collect data in various districts can cause inconsistencies, which may contribute to either an underestimation or an overestimation of enrollment numbers. This is particularly true in distant or conflict-affected areas where obtaining accurate data is challenging.

Another constraint of the study is its emphasis on quantitative data, which offers a comprehensive perspective but neglects to encompass the qualitative elements that hold equal significance. The study gives little consideration to analysing factors such as the educational standard, the unique difficulties encountered by children with disabilities, and the socio-cultural factors affecting enrollment. This quantitative focus fails to offer a comprehensive view of the educational terrain because it disregards the intricate experiences of students as well as the efficacy of instructional techniques and learning settings.

Another problem arises from the data's temporal scope. The data utilised in the study may not accurately represent the most up-to-date trends because there is a delay between collecting, analysing, and publishing the information. The temporal discrepancy suggests that the study does not account for current changes in political, social, or economic circumstances in the area, potentially affecting the significance of the results. In addition, the study lacks in-depth analysis of the socio-economic elements that impact enrollment patterns, such as household income, parental education levels, and local economic prospects. These aspects are critical for understanding the obstacles to education faced by marginalized people.

Furthermore, current policies and programmes designed to enhance educational inclusivity lack comprehensive analysis of their efficacy. To conduct a comprehensive policy-effect study, it is necessary to adopt a longer-term perspective and conduct a rigorous assessment of the existing measures. Future studies can strive to fill these voids by recognizing these constraints and offering a more comprehensive understanding of the educational environment in Jammu and Kashmir. Enhanced data gathering techniques, thorough qualitative investigations, and extensive policy analysis would greatly enhance the progress in this area of research.

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